

ON APPLYING THE MEASURES OF TECHNICAL REGULATION, STANDARDIZATION, CERTIFICATION AND IMPROVEMENT OF THE NATIONAL METROLOGY SYSTEM IN AGRICULTURE.

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Abstract: *The article provides information about standardization in the manufacturing industry and agriculture, harmonization of our existing standards with modern standards, abandonment of outdated standards.*

Keywords: *measurement uncertainty, Monte Carlo method, revision of the “Guide to the Expressing of Uncertainty in Measurement”, kurtosis method.*

19,000 of the 30,000 existing standards in the country have been harmonized with international standards and a register of international standards has been formed.

5 thousand 600 outdated standard practices that have a negative impact on the mechanisms of the market economy were removed, 3 thousand 500 were improved based on the requirements of the times. 26 additional technical regulations have been developed in accordance with international analogues. Global G.A.P. in 260 enterprises producing mainly agricultural products [1].

And based on Organic standards, a quality system was introduced and they were certified at the international level, but this means that it is difficult and trying to harmonize almost 90 percent of agricultural enterprises in all of Uzbekistan with modern standards. In order to increase agricultural products and improve their quality, to accelerate production in agro-industrial complexes, to create an effective tool for organizational and management issues, the state system of standardization and metrological support should be used in every way [2]. Wide use of control-measuring devices and automatic means in agriculture determines the level of technical development of the field.

In modern times, the use of measuring devices in the production of agricultural products has reached a high level. Among them, the most widely used and widespread are electrical measuring devices [3].

One of the main reasons for the further development of mechanization, electrification and automation in agriculture and agro-industrial complexes is the provision of simple and accurate, perfect and cheap, compact and accurate measuring instruments that can meet the requirements of the present time [4].

In Uzbekistan, it is necessary to modernize the certification body, i.e., the accredited testing laboratories, to study the quality of products brought to the country from abroad, and to provide appropriate modern equipment in this regard, which will make a great contribution to the development of Uzbekistan [5].

For example, 32 textile enterprises were certified based on the Oeko-Tex standard. 21 enterprises received a certificate confirming the "SE" marking required in the European Union.

At the same time, there are many other tasks related to standards in production, export and import processes. Some procedures are creating difficulties for entrepreneurs

For example, our national standards are inconsistent with international standards.

Proposals for solving these issues and improving procedures in the field were discussed. For example, today, 3,400 types of products require a certificate of conformity along with a sanitary-epidemiological report. Testing of imported products is carried out during customs clearance, which takes up to 60 days. Therefore, it is necessary to establish a system of placing documents in this regard in the customs electronic program at least 30 days in advance [6].

It is necessary to take into account that ecological indicators have a harmful effect on the environment during the operation or consumption of the product, it is necessary to limit the release of production waste into the natural environment, to ensure the rational use of biological resources, their preservation, and the reduction of the level of atmospheric pollution. We can give examples of ecological indicators,

the composition of toxic wastes thrown into the environment, the release of toxic gases during product operation and consumption, growth, transportation, and storage [6].

When assessing the level of product quality, it is important to take into account economic indicators that describe the differences in the preparation, production and operation of the product or in the field of consumption [7].

Economic indicators are costs for the preparation and testing of experimental samples, the cost of product production, the costs of operating technical facilities, etc [8].

Quality metrics may or may not have dimensions like physical metrics. Quantitative description of quality indicators means their measurements in certain units [9].

For example, the cost of labor used to produce a product is the time spent to produce a unit of product, expressed in man-hours. Expressing the labor cost in working days does not change the labor cost of the product [10].

Similarly, the expression of economic indicators such as the cost or price of a product in sums or other units does not change its value. Like physical quantities, the quantity of qualitative indicators can be expressed by absolute and relative quantities. The absolute value of physical quantities always has dimension, while relative quantities are dimensionless. Absolute measures of product quality can be dimensionless or dimensionless, while relative measures are always dimensionless.

References:

1. Juraboevich, Badalov Nomoz. "Products in Manufacturing Enterprises the Essence of Quality Management." *International Journal of Development and Public Policy* 1.5 (2021): 117-118.
2. Бадалов Н. Ж., Бердимуродов Г. Т., Бадалов У. Н. СИФАТЛИ МАХСУЛОТ ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИЛИШИДА СИНОВ ВА ЎЛЧОВЛАРНИНГ АХАМИЯТИ //ИЖТИМОИЙ ФАНЛАРДА INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 101-106.

3. O'g, Badalov O'tkirbek Nomoz. "THE ROLE OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN INCREASING PRODUCT QUALITY IN ENTERPRISES." *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal* 2.12 (2021): 228-233.
4. OGLI, BADALOV UTKIRBEK NOMOZ. "THE IMPORTANCE OF TESTING LABORATORIES AND THEIR ACCREDITATION."
5. Бадалов Н. Ж., Бадалов У. Н. КОРХОНАЛАРДА МАҲСУЛОТЛАР СИФАТИНИ БОШҚАРИШНИНГ АСОСИЙ ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИ //Academic research in modern science. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 38-45.
6. Jo'raboevich B. N. QUALITY EXPORT PRODUCTS IN ENTERPRISES GENERAL AND SPECIAL IN PRODUCTION IMPORTANCE OF REGULATIONS //ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 06. – С. 18-24.
7. Juraboyevich B. N., Son B. O. N. THE ROLE OF QUALITY PRODUCTION IN ENTERPRISES //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 9. – №. 10. – С. 644-647.
8. Jo'raboevich B. N., Ikramovich I. D., Nomozovich B. U. SINOV VA KALIBRLASH LABORATORIYALARIDA KOMPETENTLIGINI XALQARO DARAJADA OSHIRISH OMILLARI //E Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 128-131.
9. Juraboyevich B. N. et al. Development Of Metrology And The Role And Importance Of Metrological Supply In Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 136-139.
10. Бадалов Н. Ж., Икромов Д. И., Бадалов У. Н. КОРХОНАЛАРДА ЎЛЧАШЛАР, СИНОВЛАР ВА ТАҲЛИЛЛАРНИНГ МЕТРОЛОГИК АХАМИЯТИ //Международная конференция академических наук. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 15. – С. 11-17.